

University of
Nottingham
UK | CHINA | MALAYSIA

UNIVERSITY OF
DELAWARE

TURNEYES 892951

RESEARCHER ANNEMARIE WALTER
OUTGOING SUPERVISOR DAVID REDLAWSK
INCOMING SUPERVISOR CEES VAN DER EIJK

REPORT 12

STUDY 5:
PRIMING MORAL IDENTITY
IN PARTISAN CONTEXT

November 2024

The project Turning a Blind Eye to Scandal has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 892951

Priming Moral Identity in Partisan Context

We explored whether the laboratory experiments that had been planned could instead be conducted in an online mode. A comprehensive and systematic literature study was conducted of all published studies in which voters' moral identity was primed. It was discovered that almost all studies identified were conducted in a laboratory setting. The overview was used to identify the most frequently used stimuli in social psychology that were reported to be successful in priming voters' moral identity. Subsequently, a theoretical framework was developed that informed an experimental study design for online use (rather than laboratory use). Essential to this study was successful priming of the salience of moral identity online. A pilot survey with an embedded online experiment was conducted in Spring 2023 with a heterogenous sample of 248 US voters on Amazon Mechanical Turk. See Table 1 for the sample demographics.

Table 1 Sample Demographics

Variables	Statistics	Note
Mean Age (std.)	37.29 (17.43)	From 22 to 99
Mean Education (std.)	4.10 (1.09)	From 1 (High school) to 7 (Doctoral)
% Female	18.95	0-1
% Hispanic	23.39	0-1
Race % White	70.56	0-1 (Reference)
% Black	1.21	0-1
% Asian	6.85	0-1
% Indian/Native	21.37	0-1
Mean Religiosity (std.)	3.53 (1.40)	From 1 (Never) to 6 (Every week)
Mean Liberal (std.)	2.95 (1.09)	From 1 (Very conservative) to 5 (Very liberal)
Party % Independent	4.03	0-1 (Reference)
% Democrats	50.40	0-1
% Republicans	45.56	0-1

Prior to conducting this survey IRB approval was acquired from the University of Delaware and the University of Nottingham. The experiment consisted of 3 groups, two control groups (without priming) and one treatment group (each exposed to a different priming stimulus). The respondents were randomly assigned to one of the three groups. A randomization check shows that the random assignment was successful, see Table 2.

Table 2 Randomization Check (Y: Prime – Treatment, Control A, Control B)

Variables	Statistics	P-values
<i>Categorical</i>	χ^2 (df)	
Female	1.588 (2)	0.452
Hispanic	4.141 (2)	0.126
Race	7.151 (6)	0.307
Partisan	3.848 (4)	0.427
<i>Continuous</i>	<i>F</i> (df1, df2)	
Age	3.562 (2, 245)	0.030*
Education	2.504 (2, 245)	0.084
Religiosity	3.432 (2, 245)	0.034*
Liberal	2.583 (2, 245)	0.081

Note: The results of a multinomial logistic regression model using the variables in the table to predict experimental conditions tell us that the variables do not jointly predict the experimental conditions. (LR test: 28.744(22), $p= 0.151$)

Out of an inventory of all techniques used in experimental studies to manipulate the salience of moral identity, the handwriting task (e.g. Aquino et al. 2007; Aquino et al. 2009; Wu & Yang, 2018) was selected. The handwriting task was considered in other studies an effective stimulus for priming moral identity (e.g. Wu & Yang, 2018; Aquino et al. 2007; Aquino et al. 2009; Sanders et al. 2018; Kavussanu et al. 2015). In the treatment condition respondents were provided with nine words that are associated with being a moral person (Aquino & Reed, 2002) and the respondents were asked to write a story about themselves using these words. In the control condition A respondents were asked to write a story on how they relate to common objects in their surroundings. They were provided with nine words representing objects. In control condition B respondents were asked to write a story about themselves using the nine provided traits. The traits provided are positive, but unrelated to morality. See below the exact wording of the three tasks.

“The purpose of this exercise is to examine how people relate to the objects in the surroundings when telling stories about themselves.” Listed below are nine words in alphabetical order. Please take a few moments (about 5-10 seconds per word) to think about what each word means to you.”

Treatment

Caring, Compassionate, Fair, Friendly, Generous, Helpful, Hardworking, Honest, and Kind

Control A

Book, Car, Chair, Computer, Desk, House, Pen, Street, and Table

Control B

Carefree, Compatible, Favorable, Generally, Happy, Harmless, Open-minded, Polite, Respectable

Please write a story or a few stories about yourself **using each word at least once.**

The full survey can be found in Appendix 2. We first of all conducted a manipulation check to see whether the treatment was successful. We looked whether the treatment condition made respondents to consider themselves more of moral person than the control groups, See Figure 1.

Figure 1 Manipulation Checks

As shown in Figure 1, left column, those in the treatment condition were more inclined to perceive the stories they wrote about themselves as reflecting their moral character. However, a statistically significant difference was observed only between the treatment condition (4.071) and control group A (starting with desk: 3.384). In the same comparison (T vs. A), the treatment condition also increased the likelihood of participants perceiving their stories as reflecting their membership in an organization or their happiness. After that we looked whether the treatment increased the salience of moral identity of respondents, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: Does the Treatment Change the Level of Moral Identity?

Mean of Moral Identity ($F= 0.372 (2,245)$; $p = 0.69$)

Treatment = 3.642 (Caring, Compassionate, Fair, Friendly, Generous, Helpful, Hardworking, Honest, and Kind)

Control_A = 3.600 (Book, Car, Chair, Computer, Desk, House, Pen, Street, and Table)

Control_B = 3.668 (Carefree, Compatible, Favorable, Generally, Happy, Harmless, Open-minded, Polite, Respectable)

We do not find significant differences in respondents' scores in moral identity across the experimental conditions. Also no significant differences between the experimental groups were found when we looked at Internalization and Symbolization of moral identity (the two subscales of the moral identity scale), not visually displayed here. This is contrary to numerous studies in the literature e.g. Wu & Yang, 2018; Aquino et al. 2007; Aquino et al. 2009; Sanders et al. 2018; Kavussanu et al. 2015). The measure used to gauge moral identity is widely used and has been validated (Aquino and Reed II, 2002). In addition to measuring moral identity using the 10 item measure developed by Aquino and Reed II (2002), we looked whether the experimental conditions affected how respondents read and judged a vignette in which a fictional politician engaged in morally transgressive behavior. The scenario in this vignette is a combination of a general introduction of fictional politician Donovan, which we have been successfully using in other studies (Walter & Redlawsk, 2024). A moral transgression was added to the vignette. Previous work has shown that this act was perceived as morally transgressive by a large part of the US population (see Walter & Redlawsk, 2019). The vignette had the following text:

“Patrick Donovan is a 4-term state legislator planning to run again in the next election. He is 56 years old, married, and has two children. He attended the state university, and after graduation, he worked in the family business. You read an online news story about state politics. In the story you learn about a report that Rep. Donovan laughed out loud at a homeless voter who asked for help.”

Following the vignette the question asked was: “Thinking about the additional information you just learned about Patrick Donovan, how would you now rate him on the following characteristics?” 6 traits were provided in random order that respondents could score this fictional politician on. The results are displayed per trait for each condition in Figure 3. Only for two traits, could we find significant differences at a 95% confidence level. But the directions were counterintuitive. For example, those in the treatment group reported Donovan's behavior to be less uncompassionate (2.833) than those in other control groups did (A: 3.535, B:3.525). And also, those in the control groups evaluated Donovan's behavior as more unlikable (A: 3.372, B: 3.000) than those in other control groups did (2.702).

Figure 3. Did the Experimental Conditions Lead to Meaningful Changes in the Characteristic Evaluations?

In addition we asked to what extent respondents considered Donovan’s behavior to be legally wrong, morally wrong or inappropriate. The results of the ANOVA analysis, see Figure 4, suggested that a statistically significant difference between the experimental conditions exists solely on the legally wrong scale ($F= 4.493 (2,245); p < 0.05$). Those in the treatment condition were more inclined to report that Donovan's behavior was "legally wrong" (3.179) than those in the other control conditions (A:2.628, B:2.769). There was no such a difference on the “morally wrong” scale.

Figure 4 Did the Experimental Conditions Lead to Meaningful Changes in the Evaluations of Donovan's behavior?

Overall, the results of the pilot study were unsatisfactory and showed that the priming stimuli failed to (significantly) prime voters' moral identity. Similar results were obtained when taking a more rigorous selection of respondents, dropping respondents that took a very long time to fill in the survey. The researcher and outgoing supervisor agreed that these results were too ambiguous in relation to the social psychological literature on which the priming stimuli were based and that they therefore did not warrant a more extensive follow up. Most lab-based studies in social psychology report the effectiveness of the priming in terms of significance, but most often not in terms of effect-size. This makes it impossible to compare the effect-size in this online experiment with reported lab-based literature and to assess whether the not-significant priming effect is due to low statistical power (which could be remedied by enlarging the sample size), or by lack of control in online experiments that undermines the effectiveness of priming stimuli. MTurk does also not necessarily yield the highest quality respondents (Douglas et al. 2023; Chmielewski & Kucker 2020). The results of this pilot study were presented at a panel on morality at the 2023 Midwest Political Science Association. The researcher and outgoing supervisor have concluded that the attempt to replace these particular lab-based experiments with an online version priming respondents' moral identity showed too little promise to warrant being pursued further. The data of this pilot is available upon request from David Redlawsk. His email address is: redlawsk@udel.edu

References

- Aquino, K., Freeman, D., Reed II, A., Lim, V. K., & Felps, W. (2009). Testing a social-cognitive model of moral behavior: the interactive influence of situations and moral identity centrality. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 97(1), 123.
- Aquino, K., Reed II, A., Thau, S., & Freeman, D. (2007). A grotesque and dark beauty: How moral identity and mechanisms of moral disengagement influence cognitive and emotional reactions to war. *Journal of experimental social psychology*, 43(3), 385-392.
- Aquino, K., & Reed II, A. (2002). The self-importance of moral identity. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 83(6), 1423.
- Chmielewski, M., & Kucker, S. C. (2020). An MTurk crisis? Shifts in data quality and the impact on study results. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 11(4), 464-473.
- Douglas, B. D., Ewell, P. J., & Brauer, M. (2023). Data quality in online human-subjects research: Comparisons between MTurk, Prolific, CloudResearch, Qualtrics, and SONA. *Plos one*, 18(3), e0279720.
- Kavussanu, M., Stanger, N., & Ring, C. (2015). The effects of moral identity on moral emotion and antisocial behavior in sport. *Sport, Exercise, and Performance Psychology*, 4(4), 268.
- Reed II, A., Kay, A., Finnel, S., Aquino, K., & Levy, E. (2016). I don't want the money, I just want your time: How moral identity overcomes the aversion to giving time to prosocial causes. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 110(3), 435.
- Sanders, S., Wisse, B., Van Yperen, N. W., & Rus, D. (2018). On ethically solvent leaders: The roles of pride and moral identity in predicting leader ethical behavior. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 150, 631-645.
- Walter, A. S., & Redlawsk, D. P. (2019). Voters' partisan responses to politicians' immoral behavior. *Political Psychology*, 40(5), 1075-1097.
- Walter, A. S., & Redlawsk, D. P. (2024). The Effects of Prototypicality on Punishment of in-Party Political Leaders' Immoral Behavior. In *Scandalogy 4: Political Scandals in the Age of Populism, Partisanship, and Polarization* (pp. 157-172). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Wu, B., & Yang, Z. (2018). The impact of moral identity on consumers' green consumption tendency: The role of perceived responsibility for environmental damage. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 59, 74-84.

Appendix 1 Additional Figures and Tables

Figure 1 Boxplots of Duration by Experimental Conditions (N= 248)

Appendix 2 Survey Priming Voters' Moral Identities

Pre-Test Questionnaire 1.24.2023

[Consent]

Thank you for your interest in participating in this research study. Please read the following information and indicate if you wish to participate.

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN A RESEARCH STUDY

Principal Investigator(s): David P Redlawsk & Annemarie Walter

This study is funded by the University of Nottingham.

Important aspects of the study you should know about:

- **Purpose:** The purpose of the study is to learn how people respond to politicians and their behaviors.
- **Procedures:** If you choose to participate, you will be asked to answer questions about how you would feel if a politician exhibited certain behaviors. You will also be asked to provide some demographic information, such as your age and gender, and information about your political attitudes.
- **Duration:** This will take about 10 minutes.
- **Risks:** The main risk or discomfort from this research is that you may find it tiring to work in front of the computer answering questions. In addition, you may be exposed to information about politics that you dislike or are uncomfortable with.
- **Benefits:** You may receive an indirect benefit by learning more about the thoughts and feelings you have in response to politicians.
- **Costs and Compensation:** e.g., If you decide to participate there will be no additional cost to you and you will receive payment for your time once you complete the survey as specified by the online panel to which you belong.
- **Participation:** Taking part or not in this research study is your decision. You can decide to participate and then change your mind at any point.

Contact Information: If you have any questions about the purpose, procedures, or any other issues related to this research study you may contact the Principal Investigator, David Redlawsk, at 302-861-2357 or redlawsk@udel.edu.

Click on the YES button below will indicate your consent to use your responses in this study.

YES NO – Exit survey

[Manipulation] – Priming Moral Identity

[RANDOM ASSIGNMENT TO TREATMENT OR CONTROL]

[Treatment Group]

The purpose of this exercise is to examine how different types of self-image affect the way people tell stories about themselves.

Listed below are nine words in alphabetical order. Please take a few moments (about 5-10 seconds per word) to think about what each word means to you.

[Caring, Compassionate, Fair, Friendly, Generous, Hardworking, Helpful, Honest, and Kind]

Please write a story or a few stories about yourself using each word at least once.

[Control Group – type A]

The purpose of this exercise is to examine how people relate to the objects in the surroundings when telling stories about themselves.

Listed below are nine words in alphabetical order. Please take a few moments (about 5-10 seconds per word) to think about what each word means to you.

[Book, Car, Chair, Computer, Desk, House, Pen, Street, and Table]

Please write a story or a few stories about yourself using each word at least once.

[Control Group – type B]

The purpose of this exercise is to examine how different types of self-image affect the way people tell stories about themselves.

Listed below are nine words in alphabetical order. Please take a few moments (about 5-10 seconds per word) to think about what each word means to you.

[Carefree, Compatible, Favorable, Generally Happy, Harmless, Open-Minded, Polite, Respectable]

Please write a story or a few stories about yourself using each word at least once.

[DEMO1] – Education

Next, we will ask some questions about you that will help us categorize your responses. What is the highest level of school you have completed?

- (1) High school diploma or equivalent
- (2) Some college, no degree
- (3) Associate degree
- (4) Bachelor's degree
- (5) Master's degree
- (6) Professional degree (J.D., M.B.A., M.D. or similar)
- (7) Doctoral degree

[DEMO2] – Age

What is your age?

[DEMO3] – Gender

What is your gender?

- (1) Male
- (2) Female
- (3) Non-binary
- (4) Other, please specify _____

[DEMO4-1] – Hispanic

Are you of Hispanic, Latino, or Spanish origin?

- (1) Yes
- (2) No

[DEMO4-2] – Race

Please indicate your ethnicity or race. For this survey, Hispanic origin is not a race. Check as many as apply to you.

- (1) White
- (2) Black or African American
- (3) American Indian or Alaska Native
- (4) Asian
- (5) Native Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander
- (6) Other, please specify _____

[DEMO7] – Religiosity

How often do you attend religious services, other than social obligations such as weddings or funerals?

- (1) Never
- (2) Once a year or less

- (3) A few times a year
- (4) Once or twice a month
- (5) Almost every week
- (6) Every week or more than once a week

[POL3] – Political Ideology

In general, how would you describe your political views?

- (1) Very conservative
- (2) Conservative
- (3) Moderate
- (4) Liberal
- (5) Very liberal

[POL4] – Partisanship

Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as Democrat, Republican or what?

- (1) Democrat
- (2) Republican
- (3) Other party, please specify _____
- (4) None
- (5) Do not know

IF POL4 = 3, 4, or 5 ASK: [4-1] Do you generally think of yourself as a little closer to one of the parties than the others? If yes, which party?

- (1) Democrat
- (2) Republican
- (3) Neither Party
- (4) Do not know

IF POL4 = 1 ASK: [4-2] Would you call yourself a very strong or not very strong Democratic Party supporter?

- (1) Very strong
- (2) Not very strong

IF POL4 = 2 ASK: [4-3] Would you call yourself a very strong or not very strong Republican Party supporter?

(1) Very strong (2) Not very strong

[Moral Identity]

Listed below are some characteristics that might describe a person:

[Caring, Compassionate, Fair, Friendly, Generous, Helpful, Hardworking, Honest, and Kind]

The person with these characteristics could be you or it could be someone else. For a moment, visualize in your mind the kind of person who has these characteristics. Imagine how that person would think, feel, and act. [10 second pause]

Now that you have a clear image of what this person would be like, please indicate how much you disagree or agree with each of the following questions.

[RANDOMIZE ITEM ORDER]

Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
It would make me feel good to be a person who has these characteristics.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Being someone who has these characteristics is an important part of who I am.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often wear clothes that identify me as having these characteristics.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would be ashamed to be a person who had these characteristics.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The types of things I do in my spare time (e.g., hobbies) clearly identify me as having these characteristics.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The kinds of books and magazines that I read identify me as having these characteristics.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Having these characteristics is not really important to me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The fact that I have these characteristics is communicated to others by my membership in certain organizations.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am actively involved in activities that communicate to others that I have these characteristics.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I strongly desire to have these characteristics. o o o o o

[Manipulation Check]

We'd like you to think back to the stories you wrote about yourself at the beginning of the survey. How much does the story you wrote reflect how you see yourself, no matter whether the item is true about you:

[RANDOMIZE ITEM ITEM ORDER]

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Quite a bit	Extremely
The story reflects me as a "member of an organization"	<input type="radio"/>				
The story reflects me as a "moral" person		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The story reflects me as a "happy" person		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[EXAMINING MORAL TRANSGRESSION]

[Distractor task Writing about something else.]

Now we have another brief writing task for you.

[DISTRACTOR TASK A – GIVEN TO PARTICIPANTS WHO DID NOT RECEIVE IT AT THE BEGINNING]

The purpose of this exercise is to examine how people relate to the objects in the surroundings when telling stories about themselves.

Listed below are nine words in alphabetical order. Please take a few moments (about 5-10 seconds per word) to think about what each word means to you.

[Book, Car, Chair, Computer, Desk, House, Pen, Street, and Table]

Please write a story or a few stories about yourself using each word at least once.

[DISTRACTOR TASK B – GIVEN TO PARTICIPANTS WHO HAD ALREADY DONE DISTRACTOR TASK A]

[Control Group – type B]

The purpose of this exercise is to examine how different types of self-image affect the way people tell stories about themselves.

Listed below are nine words in alphabetical order. Please take a few moments (about 5-10 seconds per word) to think about what each word means to you.

[Carefree, Compatible, Favorable, Generally Happy, Harmless, Open-Minded, Polite, Respectable]

Please write a story or a few stories about yourself using each word at least once.

[Vignette] – Moral Transgression

[Introduction]

Next, we would like to have you consider an action of a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

[Vignette - 1]

Patrick Donovan is a 4-term state legislator planning to run again in the next election. He is 56 years old, married, and has two children. He attended the state university, and after graduation, he worked in the family business.

[DV2A] – Characteristics of the Politician

Now, thinking about what you just learned about Patrick Donovan, how would you rate him on the following characteristics?

[RANDOMIZE ITEM ORDER]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Immoral	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	Moral

Incompetent	<input type="radio"/>	Competent						
Unlikeable	<input type="radio"/>	Likeable						
Untrustworthy	<input type="radio"/>	Trustworthy						
Uncompassionate	<input type="radio"/>	Compassionate						

Now we have some more information about Patrick Donovan for you to read.

[Vignette – 2]

You read an online news story about state politics. In the story you learn about a report that Rep. Donovan laughed out loud at a homeless voter who asked for help.

[DV2B] – Characteristics of the Politician

Thinking about the additional information you just learned about Patrick Donovan, how would you now rate him on the following characteristics?

[RANDOMIZE ITEM ORDER]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Immoral	<input type="radio"/>	Moral						
Incompetent	<input type="radio"/>	Competent						
Unlikeable	<input type="radio"/>	Likeable						
Untrustworthy	<input type="radio"/>	Trustworthy						
Uncompassionate	<input type="radio"/>	Compassionate						

[DV5] – Inappropriateness

Thinking about Donovan’s behavior toward the homeless voter, how inappropriate is his behavior for a politician?

- (1) Not at all inappropriate
- (2) Not too inappropriate
- (3) Somewhat inappropriate
- (4) Very inappropriate
- (5) Extremely inappropriate

[DV6] – (Morally) Wrongness

Thinking about Donovan’s behavior toward the homeless voter, how morally wrong is it?

- (1) Not at all morally wrong
- (2) Not too morally wrong
- (3) Somewhat morally wrong
- (4) Very morally wrong
- (5) Extremely morally wrong

[DV7] – (Legally) Wrongness

Thinking about Donovan’s behavior toward the homeless voter, how legally wrong is it?

- (1) Not at all legally wrong
- (2) Not too legally wrong
- (3) Somewhat legally wrong
- (4) Very legally wrong
- (5) Extremely legally wrong

[DV8] – Realism

Thinking about Donovan’s behavior toward the homeless voter, how realistic is it, that is, how likely is it that it could occur in American politics?

- (1) Not at all likely
- (2) Not too likely
- (3) Somewhat likely
- (4) Very likely
- (5) Extremely likely

[THANKS]

Thank you for participating in this study. Your responses will be very helpful to our understanding of how people react to politicians who might or might not violate moral principles.